

Restoring Lost Moral Values in Africa: The Tanzanian Context

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Abstract

The erosion of traditional moral values in Africa, particularly in Tanzania, has become a pressing concern in contemporary society. Practices such as hospitality, chastity before marriage, and respect for the elderly are increasingly overshadowed by rampant issues including abuse of political power, human rights violations, corruption, and substance abuse. The rise of social maladies such as pedophilia, divorce, rape, homosexuality, and abortion further signals a profound moral decline that poses challenges to familial cohesion and societal stability.

This article explores the historical context of these moral values, examines their decline within the Tanzanian context, and advocates for a multifaceted approach to moral restoration. By engaging community professionals, leaders, fostering educational initiatives, and promoting impressive traditional practices, the restoration of moral values can contribute to societal healing and progress. Recognizing the complexities of these issues is essential for developing effective strategies that honor both cultural heritage and contemporary human rights.

Keywords: *Morals, values, hospitality, corruption, human rights.*

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Introduction

In African society, each stage of human being's growth carries values attached to the people concerned. These stages of life are birth, childhood, adult hood and old age. Life to an African is celebrated and cheered and death is considered as a completion. Between life and death an African is raised and taught how to live in the society amongst other fellow humans. The African cultures are embedded within their way of life and are related to their nature.

African possesses several distinctive set of values that guide the moral behavior of every member of the society. Such values are like hospitality, chastity, truth, respect for the elderly, hard work and good character. Life in Africa is considered to be something precious and highly esteemed. "Morality can be referred to actions, or to the way human beings perform actions. In any case, morality is the quality of actions or agents by which they are in conformity with certain norms of human conduct" (Farrah, 1979). On the other hand, "Moral values refer to a set of principles that guide an individual on how to evaluate

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right versus wrong. People generally apply moral values to justify decisions, intentions and actions and it also defines the personal character of the person" (Kamili, 2017).

In his work, 'Does Morality Change? Sean Fagan adds that "Morality is not primarily about duty and obligation, but about relationships and growth" (Fagan, 2003). Morality as Fagan puts it can be understood in various ways: "in language and culture and through language and consciousness human being are self mutually enriched and their growth speed up" (Fagan, 2003). Language gives us an evidence that it grew from the exchange of mere practical information to the communication of ideas and deeper levels of personal sharing. "Language, behavior and myth are intertwined and inter-dependent" (Fagan, 2003).

"In this way morality and religion are linked, and quite often obedient to the rule of the society, is seen as obedience to the deity and divine punishment is expected for misbehavior" (Kamili, 2017).

This flow of thought invites us to search for the African morals, values, on what they really are and on their sources and characteristics.

"Moral values refer to a set of principles that guide an individual on how to evaluate right versus wrong. People generally apply moral values to justify decisions, intentions and actions and it also defines the personal character of a person" (Kamili, 2017).

Moral values originate from, parenting and family, schools, Religious affiliation, culture, the state and peer guidance. It can be classified as either personal, family or societal.

Some Abandoned African Moral Values

Hospitality

One of the moral values that Africans can be proud of is their hospitality. A value that extends outside the family level.

"African traditions of hospitality are deep and sincere. When a person approaches a house in Kenya or Tanzania, the first thing the house holder will say is *karibu* the Swabili word for ("come close or welcome") Hospitality is a very important cultural and social value in African society. It is a way of life that is intimately bound up with personal relationships and community. A visitor is considered to be a benevolent envoy, a good luck charm, and even a savior (blessing)" (Healey, & Sybertz, 1996).

Chastity Before Marriage

In the past in some African societies it was considered shameful for a girl to be pregnant before marriage. This is to mean that chastity before marriage was much emphasized in Africa than it is today. According to the Catechism of the Catholic Church, chastity is the virtue associated with sexuality. It consists in self mastering, in guiding the sexual instinct to the service of love and personal growth. "Chastity means the successful integration of sexuality within the person and thus inner unity of man in his bodily and spiritual being" (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008). Chastity before Marriage is not kept asunder to African culture, nor it is a foreign value to Africa, but it is within the veins and back born of the African cultural values Tanzania being one of them. According to a Dictionary of Christian Ethics, "chastity is a preservation of sexual purity according to one's state of life-virginity for the unmarried, continence for the widowed, loyalty to husband or wife for the married" (Macquarrie, 1974). While emphasizing on morals related to chastity the Christian council of Tanzania affirms that it is always good to take precautions.

"Dunia imejazana vitu vingi vya kumpendeza sana ambavyo unaweza kufikiria badala ya kufikiri habari za wanawake au wanaume. Msichana usikubali wanaume au wawilana wakubusu au kukukumbatia. Pia usikae na kijana peke yenu wawili faraghani wala usiwawazje kutenda nao maovu" (Christian Council of Tanzania, 1970).

Respect for the Elderly

The concept of elders in Africa draws its meaning from the understanding of Jesus Christ Himself as the 'Ancestor of Christians', and brother, intercessor and mediator. "In African traditional society the first-born boy or brother or eldest brother had a special honor and privilege.... The eldest son received the family inheritance from his father" (Healey, & Sybertz, 1996). It was common in Africa to find a young lady or boy travelling in a bus giving a seat to an elderly, helping an elderly, or start greeting an elderly as a sign of respect, but these days with modernity it is becoming a rare value. It is up to researchers to find out the cause of this issue, which has caused the growing gap between elders and the youth in Africa. Majority of the youths in Africa today resist admonitions, hold an unlimited hubris and lack chivalry. Because of this awkward and uncouth behaviors Africa and Tanzania in particular shall from time to time have awkward leaders. Parenting should not be left for house maids, rather parents themselves should be full involved. Educators in all schools should put emphasis on morals.

Visible Indications of Moral Decadence

Africa therefore notices some visible changes that happen in the sphere of morals such as: abuse of political power, violation of human rights, corruption, drugs and substances abuse, pedophilia, divorce, rape, homosexuality and abortion.

Abuse of Political Power

Africa has from time to time been experiencing the abuse of political power from her leaders. There have been tendencies of manipulations of the constitutions to suit some regimes which is in fact an act against the will of the citizens. Africa has witnessed a lot of '*coup de tat*', wars and social unrest in many countries. Some leaders have forced to overstay in power and have led their countries with an iron fist, suppressing and assassinating those leaders in oppositions. This inept handling of powers has provided a fertile land for unending wars in Africa. This has led Africans into poverty. Good and stable politics lacks in many African countries. There are leaders who overstay in power irrespective of the constitutions of their countries. Uganda, and Rwanda in East Africa are few of them; we see the heads of states of these countries suppressing opposition leaders and seek to stay in power for life long, 'they are there to stay'. All these are indicators of abuse of power and the contributors to the culture of death. Such immoral tendencies perpetrate the inter-tribal conflict and genocide.

"I was sleeping in the back room of the commune's office when someone knocked on the door and called out that President Habyarimana had died in a plane crash. Within minutes the office was crowded with people wanting to know the names of those who had killed our beloved president. I told them that members of the Tutsi revolutionary party, the RPF, might have planned such evils. Now it was time to get rid of our real enemy, the Tutsi" (Pierce, 1999).

Expecting development in a troubled land is unrealistic, poverty will emerge as civilians' cannot involve themselves in building their economy. They have land, they are the man power themselves but, no peace, bad and corrupt leadership make a back-sliding economy, enhancing to poverty. As result, poverty in Africa has become rampant.

¹Translation: The World is full of beautiful things, which someone might be occupied with rather than just thinking about women or men. Girl, you should not allow men or women kiss or hug you. Either do not sit closer to a man or woman when you are only two of you in a private place and you should not think of doing evil. Cf., CHRISTIAN COUNCIL OF TANZANIA, Ndoa Iliyo Bora, 197.

"Various socio-economic and political theories have been proposed to explain the causes of African's poverty. The rise into power of ruthless dictators and oppressive military rulers who have siphoned resources from their countries in order to remain in power. Greed, corruption and ethnicity" (Kanyandago, 2002).

According to Julius Nyerere, the first president of Tanzania; in order for any nation to achieve development, four things are inevitably important; (a) people, (b) land (c) good politics and (d) good leadership. He writes:

*"Maendeleo ya nchi huitwa na watu, bayaletwi na fedha. Fedha ni matokeo sio msingi wa maendeleo. Ili tuendeleo twabitaji vitu vinne: (i) Watu (ii) Ardhi (iii) Siasa safi, na (iv) Uongozi bora"*².

Violation of Human Rights

The first right of a human being is certainly the right to life. The violation of human rights entails as well going against the rule of law, it involves abduction, unlawful detaining of civilians for long without trial and ruthless killings. Before we tackle the concept of human rights it is worthy to discuss on the notion of 'right'.

"According to the classical axiom; *ius est ad alios* (a right is a relationship to others; it is the arrangement of the interpersonal relationship), only relations of one person to another person belong to the world of rights in the strict sense of the word (therefore it includes neither the relations of persons to things...nor the relations between a person and his own personal goods)." (Bruger, & Baker, 1972).

According to Brugger and Bakers Philosophical dictionary the word 'right' must serve to designate three things; the juridical order, and also every particular juridical norm which forms a part of this order (*ius normativum*); and that which corresponds to the juridical order or to the particular juridical norms, whether it is a structure, a circumstance or human conduct and the powers which belong to the members of a juridical ordered community (Bruger, & Baker, 1972). Since rights concern the relations between persons in a community only, only persons can be the subjects of rights and duties. Human rights therefore are the fundamental rights that belong to an individual as consequence of being human. Rights are safeguards that protect the interest of the rights bearer.

Once they attain power, African leaders are normally surrounded by a coterie of people who are only friends of the leaders' office and not essentially their true friends. They are summoned by shared interests, especially those interests that exclude other people of lower class. Some African leaders are people who lack character, like being worshiped as minor deities, hostile to truth, arrogant and attracted to flattery. They lack focus, intellectual stamina, detachment, lack humility, and spiritual emptiness, unconstitutional, and wealth seekers. Once they are in power, they are there to stay just like chiefs.

Basic Human Rights

The United Nations Charter states what the international human community believes to be basic human rights. Such rights are proclaimed in the two International Covenants. "Man's life comes from God; it is his gift, his image and imprint, a sharing in his breath of life. God therefore is the sole Lord of this life: man cannot do with it as he wills" (John Paul II, 1995).

"On the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights states such rights as; right to life, and liberty, freedom from slavery and torture, freedom of opinion and expression, the right to work and education, security of person; freedom from arbitrary arrest, detention or exile; right to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, freedom of thought, conscience and religion; and freedom of peaceful assembly and association" (United Nations, 2024).

² Translation: Development of any country depends on people not necessarily money. Money is just an outcome or result, and not the basis of development. In order to develop we need four things:(i) People (ii) Land (iii) Good politics and (iv) Good leadership. Cf., NYERERE, J.K., Ujamaa, p. 27.

In the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights specifies the following rights to be basic on the economic, social and cultural sphere; the right to social security; right to work; the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living including adequate food, clothing and housing; right of everyone to education; right to participate in the cultural life of the community; and right to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits (World Health Organization, n.d.).

In the social teaching of the Catholic Church, especially in the Encyclical *Pacem in Terris* a list of human rights is explained. The Catholic Church's category of basic human rights, thus, is the following: Civil rights (right to life, liberty, and security), economic rights, thus, is as following: civil rights (right to life, liberty, and security), economic rights (rights to work, to a just wage, to property), economic rights (rights to work, to a just wage, to property), social rights (rights to assembly, to free association), political rights (right to vote, right to equality before the law), political rights (right to vote, to equality before the law, to emigrate or immigrate), cultural rights (right to education, to freedom of speech), and religious rights (right to worship) (John XXIII, 1963). Scholars assert that in a strict sense human rights are therefore mainly of two types; freedoms and demands.

Theories of Rights

There are many theories of rights as there are rights theorists. The concept of rights can be categorized into three aspects; rights as claims, interests and trumps. This clarification of rights indicates some different ways in which rights have been understood.

"Ideally, a theory of rights will provide a working analysis of the concept of rights, elucidate a preferred justification for having rights and set of values for determining the proper content of rights, and identify the empirical assumptions that underpin such recommendations" (Campbell, 2005).

By right as a claim, in the first theory scholars explain that a right is more than just a claim for an object; it is a claim against someone that is a respondent. This means a rapport between one claiming and the duty bearer, which have distinctive ethical implications. The second theory views rights as entitlements or interests. The question here is, for whose interest are the rights claims made? "the focus here is on the right-holder, that is, the subject of the rights. What is mainly crucial here is that of being rights to, not rights against. And the third theory is that of considering right as trumps. Humans rights are taken to stand for the strongest moral claims available.

Rights as Claims

The basic notion of a claim is a call (Lat. *clamare*) for the acceptability of something admittedly contestable. Etymologically, a claim means calling out- to cry out, or to shout. "Rights are claimed only when enjoyment of the object of the right is threatened or denied. In this context, claims of human rights are the final resort in claiming rights" (Rwiza, 2010). Rights are thus claims that have achieved a special kind of endorsement: legal rights by legal system. The linkage between rights and duties facilitates the understanding of rights as claims. In this linkage the main focus is on the subject of the right. Alan Gewirth is one of the theorists who conceive rights as claims. In his book, entitled "Human Rights: Essays on Justification and Application, he allocates the components of rights in the following view:

"There are five main elements here; first the subject (A) of the right, the person who has it; second, the nature of the right; the objects (X) of the right, what it is a right to; fourth, the respondent (B) of the right, the person or persons who have the correlative duty; and fifth, the justifying basis or ground (Y) of the right" (Gewirth, 1983).

A right always entails a duty, just as it is a duty of an all human beings and specifically expectants to care for the un born human being. That means a right is more than it is in legal terms, that is just a claim against someone who is a respondent. In viewing rights as claims Gerwirth considered a will theory, which focuses on the human agency and human action. He employs the concept of agency to establish basic rights as the necessary prerequisites of being an agent. The basis therefore for justifying the binding forces of rights as claims is the subject of the right. The will theory contends that all powers pertaining

to a duty must rely with the claim - holder, if he or she is to be a right holder. This indicates that a right holder is that person in whom all those powers lies.

Rights as Entitlements or Interests

After discussion about the rights as claims we distinguish the second theory, which considers rights as entitlement or interests. Rights are conceived as rights to as in the case of the rights to life, freedom and happiness - not as rights against. The fundamental notion underlying the interest theory is that every right protects some aspects of a person's welfare, which may or may not include some aspects of the person's freedom. This is the basic character of a right.

The concept of interest treats rights as a means of promoting individual welfare. Advocates of the interests' theory approach argue that the principal function of human rights is to protect and promote certain essential human interests. "The notion of rights as interest can protect children and their interests against abuse, exploitation and commercialization" (Rwiza, 2010). The notion underlying the interest theory is that every right protects some aspects of the people's welfare. The interest theory focuses passively on the subject of the right, that is, the recipient of the object.

Rights as Trumps

The third theory is that of conceiving rights as trumps. Rights are understood as trumps used by individuals to frustrate the overreaching collective demands made by large groups in society. A legal philosopher, Ronald Dworkin considers rights as trumps founded on the equality of respect and concern.³ The rights of a family are trumps used to protect it. He added that rights as trumps entails that someone claiming a right to a political act is claiming that those in a position to provide it cannot justifiably refuse to do so for utilitarian or wealth-maximizing reasons. "If the government does not take rights seriously, then it does not take law seriously either" (Beauchamp, 1991).

Living a Culture of Life.

In the Gospel of John, Jesus teaches that he is the Lord of life. He assumed the role of provider and guardian of eternal life. "I have come that they may have life." Jn; 10:10.

"The culture of life is a term used in Moral theology to describe the theological truth of human life that all stages of human life from conception to natural death is sacred". In this light the culture of life opposes practices which involves destruction of human life such as abortion, euthanasia, the use of embryonic stem cells for medical research and studies, artificial contraceptives, capital punishment, unjust war suicide and assisted suicide, mutilation, narcissism, and excessive selfishness. These are what John Paul II described as culture of death" (John XXIII, 1963).

In Africa the weakening of the culture of life has greatly declined the human dignity. The increasing spread of destruction of human life and the equal system is being observed almost everywhere.

The meaning of bodily life as an exalted good is no longer valued though from time to time the Church teaches that a person's prime concern is for his own life. The Christians consider that time of earthly pilgrimage as a unique "KAIROS"⁴ that is it is a time of favor in which a person is tried and tested. It is a time allotted for growth in love of God and neighbor. It is a time to give the best of oneself for the benefit of human kind today and of future generation. It is therefore a time to personify love, goodness, joy, peace and justice, etc.

³"Taking Rights Seriously" in Dworkin Ronald, in one of his best treatises, became famous for his defense for 'legal realism', that is the integral place that moral and pragmatic views play in legal decision-making in opposition to what he sees as their exclusion by legal positivism.

⁴KAIROS means God- given time of grace, and opportunity. Cf., G. LOBO, Moral Theology Today, Christian Living According to Vatican II, p. 89, 326. Is one of the root concepts in Christian ethics, based on the recognition that all gifts come from God and must be used to his glory, whether the money, time or talents. The Roman Catholic thought has perhaps gone furthest in working out its wider implications, on the basis of the teaching of the medieval Church. The concept of the just price and the just wage are themselves applications of stewardship.

God is the meaning of life, each one of us is an enigma to himself. God gives us a finite existence and is completely free whether to give existence or not. There is nothing about us which lays claim to exist. One's existence is one's but at the same time God's property given it to one for his sake to serve God's purposes. Thus every finite being exists for one reason and only to manifest the goodness of God each on its own level.

A person has uniqueness, his value is incalculable and his preciousness is beyond human computation. So, one must and should not be violated by any person. No price - tag attached to one's living because God has given one's life and has put it in price range beyond all considerations of usefulness, cleverness, attractiveness, or any other relative criteria. Hence the value of any person does not consist in what one is.

One is unique image of God with responsibility of free and actualizing that image which one alone can make actual. That is the meaning or purpose of one's creation and continued existence. That is why one's existence should not be interfered with at any stage of life whether one is in poverty or in a full vigor, in living or struck down by incapacitating illness or old and senile. That is why also human generative process should not be tempered with by an unchaste hand, for instance abortion, and euthanasia. The moral inviolability of the person extends back to the process of his/her becoming. Farther back even than one's actual conception to those mysterious activities that are going on within the bodies of man and woman designed by God as means of bringing a person into being in cooperation with divine creation.

Human existence therefore once it has been directed into actuality with God stands beyond people's right to temper with it. So, the purpose of our existence gives us greater dignity than that of Earthly beings. We as human beings have an obligation to continue in creators' path, to live in a destined manner a life which carries with it the right to life. If we see this in ourselves, we should as well see to it that our neighbor has the same right to live and we have the obligation to let our neighbor see that each person is a unique and reputable being.

Stewardship of Life

Exercising our God given dominion over his creation is what it exactly means "stewardship"⁵ of life. From the very beginning human person has been endowed with a two-fold uniqueness. They bear God image consisting of rational, moral, social and spiritual activities which makes it possible for human person to know him. They also exercise dominion over creation. So stewardship is concerned with creators' gift and the way we use them. It should have the power to shape our understanding of our lives to the respect for human life protecting life from threat and assault.

The stewardship therefore is a cooperative dominion in exercising the God given dominion. One is not creating the processes of nature but cooperating with them. It is true that one should utilize one's talents to improve one's human life. Nevertheless, in all these activities one is cooperated with the laws of fruitfulness that God has already established. It is a responsible dominion.

In one of his treatises Bernard Haring emphasizes that every person and every group must absolutely respect the sacredness of each human person and contribute to the growth of the freedom of all. Stewardship must not be exercised in a loveless attitude but in a spirit of reverence to one's life and life of others.

Bodily life is entrusted to a person freely as a most precious gift. As such, we are not independent masters of our life but only steward subjects toward sovereignty of God. Christ exemplifies these to the extent to which a person can surrender his/her life. To be able to lay it down if need be for the sake of others as

⁵ Stewardship: Is one of the root concepts in Christian ethics, based on the recognition that all gifts come from God and must be used to his glory, whether the money, time or talents. The Roman Catholic thought has perhaps gone furthest in working out its wider implications, on the basis of the teaching of the medieval Church. The concepts of the just price and the just wage are themselves applications of stewardship.

a witness to faith, love and hope, such is life entrusted to the love of others and the responsibility of human health.

Emphasizing the African traditional life on good cultural values, which are worth preserving. As to why moral standards are declining or being lost these days than before is that; many reasons were given in order to put emphasis on morals:

"Good conduct leads to harmony between man and God, observance of the law governed the community and society, there was more peace, people with 'good manners' were highly respected, leaders needed these virtues, better prestige, morals shaped and sharpened the youth to become responsible, good deeds shaped the individual and society, morals intensified the community into a corporate unity. The aspect of fear was not lacking: deviance was severely punished, those who neglected morals were despised, malady could befall, out-casting of deviants, no proper burial after death, not joining the ancestors in the World to come, a social evil for the family and clan" (Mwikamba, 1992).

Corruption

In Africa, corruption has become a cancer to the society. Corrupt practices are overt in our society. Our society experiences greed civil society workers who seek to accumulate worth for an over-night, they squander the government money mercilessly and at the expense of the tax payers. Fraudsters are being reported almost everywhere in Africa. The gap between the rich and the poor is widening from day to day.

"Corruption in all its forms is a kind of deterioration of moral standards in society. Its negative impact is reflected clearly in the loss of moral values, and a progressive reduction in the ability to act in a morally non-corrupt manner among persons and public officials" (Tarimo, 2005).

Drugs and Substances Abuse

*"Madawa ya kulerya ni janga la kitaifa kwa vijana na bata watu wazima nchini Tanzania. Janga hili sasa limeenea hadi vijijini. Tokana na hali hii, nguvu kazi ya Taifa kiuchumi imedhoofika. Natoa wito kwa viongozi wa dini zote kupaza sauti zao kukemea janga hili katika jamii yetu"*⁶.

The virtue of temperance calls upon human beings to abstain from every kind of excess. excessive use of food, alcohol tobacco or medicine, all damage the body. Those incur grave guilt who over speed because of either being drunk or not, endanger themselves and others safety, on the road, sea, or air (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008). Drugs and substance abuse have been one of the enormous damage and a set back to the youth in Africa. Reasons as to why people use drugs and alcoholic substances is of great discussion. "The use of drugs make very grave damage on human health and life. Clandestine production of and trafficking in drugs are scandalous practices" (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008). Related to drugs is alcoholism which is again detrimental to health.

"Alcoholism is a disease in which the addictive cycle starts with a compulsion to drink in order to drown the effects of previous drinking. While excessive repetitive drinking causes physical complications, particularly vitamin B1 deficiency, the basic problem is the motive for repetition. The disease involves body, mind and soul. Excessive alcohol intake depresses the self-critical centers giving an elusive sense of confidence eventually dissipated in a 'hangover' but dependence increases tensions" (Hewitt, 1988).

It makes a big difference between an ordinary drinker and an excessive drinker. The excessive drinker lives to drink, but the alcoholic drinks to live; while the excessive drinker can control his or her drinking

⁶ Translation: Drug abuse in Tanzania is a national disaster. Both the youth and the middle aged men and women use drugs. This disaster has spread even to the villages. Because of this, the economic man power has been weakened. I call upon for a religious leader to raise their voices to rebuke it with all efforts untiringly. Cf. KASSIM MAJALIWA, Speech at *Maulid* Feast in Dodoma, Tanzania Broad Casting Corporation, 28 September, 2023.

at a decisive crisis and may continue to enjoy it, the alcoholic cannot. The alcoholic is normally trapped by alcohol in a tension of helpless dependence on it.

"Alcoholism may be define as a conscious or subconscious irresistible, persistent urge for an alcoholic beverage that leads its victim to drink regardless of the circumstances or less of the circumstances, in spite of any hardship or suffering it may cause to himself or others" (Hewitt, 1988).

In real sense, a rational and moderate consumption of alcohol is not bad. History tells us that Monks for centuries have brewed beer and wine to support their monasteries. What is morally bad is overdosing or over drinking, it is debauchery. St. Paul speaks of drinking alcohol multiple times. In Rom 13:13, Paul urges us to walk as if it were day time instead of taking part in the things that people usually do under the cover of darkness. Orgies, drunkenness, promiscuity and licentiousness are discouraged by Paul. In the letter to Ephesians, 5:18, Paul emphasizes on not to get drunk on wine, because drunkenness leads to debauchery. In the letter to Galatians Paul (Gal, 5:19-21), Paul classifies drunkenness as one of the works of the flesh. Excessive alcohol leads to loss of the ability to control oneself. "Usually the alcoholic will lose his ability to control his drinking towards the end of the initial phase or at the beginning of the middle phase" (Gelinis, 2013). Even if someone does not drink and drive, excessively alcohol consumption greatly impairs one's ability to reason. In Tanzania, people under 18 are not allowed to drink alcohol.

Pedophilia

In Africa and Tanzania in particular pedophilia is being reported to happen mostly in Primary schools. A good number of reasons are being attributed to it; but the main allegation is thrown to tutors who opt to abuse the teenagers by either threatening or by use of petty bait-gifts. Incidences of teenage pregnancies has a broader scope; it occurs also in the society, in streets, towns, as well as cities. Teenage pregnancies are basically a result of pedophilia; it means: "when an adult engages in sexual relations or intimacy with a person who is underage. The definition of underage varying according to a local age of consent laws, but the World average is 16 years old" (Kamili, 2017).

Unlike these days, where modern society is claimed to be sex free and immoral; in the past, the African morals emphasis was placed on: "avoidance of pre-marital and extra-marital sex, faithfulness in marriage, incest taboos and lack of sexual abuse (children). A recent report shows that sexual jealousy, adultery and separation are among the leading causes of murder" (Mwikamba, 1992).

Divorce

The African society is being influenced greatly with other cultures through media and other means of interactions. This counter-cultural interaction leaves no culture unaltered. Married couples are not left untouched, they are in trouble as well. "The ignorance of the functions and powers of the mind is the cause of all marital trouble. Marriage to be real must first be on a spiritual basis. It must be of the heart, and the heart is the chalice of love" (Murphy, 2020).

"The term divorce is used for two different conditions. The first is divorce '*a mensa et thoro*', from table and bed, more accurately defined as separation. In this case the partners to a marriage live separately and cease to co - habit, but neither is free to remarry another person while the partner is still living. The second sense of divorce is divorce '*a vinculo*' by which is meant the dissolution of the bond of marriage leaving the partners free to marry again as if they have never married in the first place. Such divorce is incompatible with the doctrine of the indissolubility of marriage" (Macquarrie, 1974).

Divorce in Africa is mainly caused by a number of reasons such as; domestic violence, unfaithfulness or extra-marital sexuality, impotence, bareness or infertility, lack of trust between spouses, and family pressure. The Catechism of the Catholic Church affirms that; "Adultery, divorce, polygamy, and free union are grave offences against the dignity of marriage" (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008).

Rape

Rape refers to a forceful sexual act which is against the will or consent of one part. The increase of rape marks one of the mentioned criminal events in the society. The alarming percentage of criminality and anti-social behavior are being reported almost everywhere in Africa. According to the Catechism of the Catholic Church;

"Rape is the forcible violation of the sexual intimacy of another person. It does injury to justice and charity. Rape deeply wounds the respect, freedom and physical and moral integrity to which every person has a right. It causes grave damage that can mark the victim for life. It is always an intrinsically evil act." (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008).

The criminality events among the youth rise in our society carrying with it a number of consequences such as tearing apart the harmony of the society, development retardation, to mention just a few of them. Rape was originally considered to be caused by an unbridled sexual desire but these days it is understood as "a pathological assertion of power over a victim" (Britannica, n.d.). Several causes have been attributed to be the causes of rape; such are indecent dress and make ups, obsession for sex desire to control, war-rapes committed with impunity, rape myths, such as 'no means yes' which is associated with claims that a lady can never say yes; women like to be taken by force, drunkenness, women who drink are an easy lay, they admit to force sex, lack of safety measures in villages where as women have to venture out at night as there are no toilet facilities in doors; this puts them at risk.

In the past, African sexual morals were good, these included: faithfulness in marriage, protection of premarital sex, value of virginity, value of virginity, there were few illegitimate children, incest taboos, no prostitution, lack of sex abuse, no rapes (severely punished) (Mwikamba, 1992).

Homosexuality

Human sexuality is rooted in man's vocation to love, which is essentially a gift from the creator. Homosexuality is morally wrong. It is not negligible in our society in Africa. It is an abomination that is extremely offensive and unacceptable. The Bible also highly condemns homosexuality such as in; (Lev; 18:22; 20:13; Deut; 23:17-18; 1Cor 6:9; 1Tim; 1:10;). Some organizations in Africa are promoting homosexuality. The Catechism of Catholic Church puts it clear that homosexual practices is one among the four sins gravely contrary to chastity.

Homosexuality is a personal, not a kind of behavior as such. Being personal does not minimize it's being a sin in itself. The main purpose of sexual intercourse is procreation and the consequent upbringing of children. Opposing the main purpose of sexual intercourse is a sin (Macquarrie, 1974).

"Among the 'sins'⁷ gravely contrary to chastity are masturbation, fornication, pornography, and homosexuality" (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008). The Catechism of the Catholic Church defines homosexuality to be "relations between men or between women who experience an exclusive or predominant sexual attraction towards persons of the same sex" (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008).

When the Catholic teaches that homosexuality is sin it really means that marital intercourse has the purpose of increasing love and subduing concupiscence.

"The loving, permanent union between man and a woman who desire to have children raise them affectionately and provide mutual help throughout the vicissitudes of life for the begetting and education of children" (TFP Committee on American Issues, 2004).

⁷ According to St. Thomas, a sin, in human acts, is that which is against the order of reason. Now the order of reason consists in its ordering everything to its end in a fitting manner.... [A]nd just as the use of food is directed to the preservation of life in the individual, so is the use of venereal acts directed to the preservation of the whole human race. (St. Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologica*, II-II, q. 153, a. 2)

Homosexuality does not result into procreation and upbringing of children, for it is basically against nature. God our creator did not plan that human beings would engage in same sex whether between men or between women.

"Homosexuality generally disposes the subject of self - expression in physical acts with others of the same sex, and when moral or social restraints are weak or absent there may be occasional or habitual indulgence into some kind of homosexuality. In certain circumstances, for example segregation in a single-sex environment, heterosexuals may resort to substitutive acts of homosexuality; or they may do so viciously, experimentally, or as prostitutes" (Bailey, 1974).

Modern Africa has its dark side, an ugly side that brings with it faces of not valuing human life. An era full of abortion, infanticide, genocide and mass killing.

"We have just seen the dark face of modernity in violence, thefts, drug addiction, promiscuity and abortions which are denounced by fundamentalists who attribute them to a loss of traditional values, and who advocate a return to them. Definitely, there is a loss of traditional values. I suggest that this loss is largely due to economic changes" (Joinet, 2000).

Abortion

Abortion is real, and a global disquieting topic in our modern society. It's controversy and diversity of approaches to it attracts attention from theologians, and non-theologians, and mostly moralists with a keen eye to what it means the dignity of human life. Perspectives to abortion are diverse, and are important for our current and future research on abortion. Abortion is generally understood as the lethal attack on the fetus or the termination of a fetus amidst gestation period. It consists in putting an end to all the crucial prerequisites that an embryo or a fetus needs for survival. It is, therefore, an act of killing prenatal life.

"Direct abortion, that is to say, abortion willed either as an end or a means, is gravely contrary to the moral law" (The Catechism of the Catholic Church, 2008).

"While speaking about family planning Dr. Abeid of Dar es Salam reported that women are dying in great numbers because they are brought at the hospital while bedridden. They end up dying because at the time they are brought at the hospital, they have already been poked in their genitals. When diagnosed they are normally found with cassava sticks inserted into their genitals in order to abort. Our responsibility as medical practitioners are to save lives. Almost in every three women who are brought at Temeke hospital being bedridden are normally those who have either attempted abortion and failed or those with post - abortion complication like excessive bleeding" (Simbaya, 2016).

Mass medias, and newspapers, all report from day to day cases of abortion, rape, drug use, incest, homosexuality and the like are being reported, almost in many places of Tanzania. What could be meaningful step for us to take today is to seek strategies of uprooting these indicators, especially those that crosses the limits of humanity such as abortion. Some of the serious moral questions that are raised concerning abortion includes; When does a human life begin? When does a human life which is morally equal to our own begin? Does all human life have value, or are some human lives not worth living, like in cases of a child with serious disabilities? Does a woman have a right to withdraw the support of her body from the fetus? What does the right to life involve?

The Role of the Church in Addressing Cultures of Life Versus Cultures of Death as indicators of Lost Moral Values

We are all affected by the cultures of life and death, we cannot avoid it. The first role of the Church in this regard is to serve the gospel of hope. (Mt; 25:40). To give the renewed hope to the poor, the marginalized, exploited and oppressed. To encourage young people, engaged couple's families, priests

and religious to live and spread the gospel of life to strengthen the cultures of life and fighting the cultures of death so as to build a city worth of man and woman. To show with complete charitable initiatives her struggle toward promoting culture of life and fight the culture of death. To strengthen the service of love to the sick, abandoned, homeless, and refugees, in order to build a more just World. To evangelize the media versus spreading culture of death like rape, etc.

Conclusion

All cultures emerge, grow, borrow some values from other cultures just like it is for languages. Good cultural values are nurtured and encouraged. It is up to the African societies to cherish good cultures and pass them from one generation to another. Since it is not too late to retrieve the moral values in Africa, despite the current moral back - sliding and decadence. The African moral values are not beyond remedy, they need to be reviewed and see a possibility to retrieve them. It all needs a creative envisioning, nurturing the embryo of self - discipline, will power and determination. Encourage mass media, in dealing with the matter, involve community mobilization, education and conscientisation. A government commitment to start educating the youths to become patriotic, 'women empowerment' (Joinet, 2000), as they are the first educators of the family and society at large and encouraging of both men and women to fully participate in the formation and education of children will help eradicate this tendency. The church in Africa should seek to intensify ways to liberate the society from this up - coming immoral generation. Values such as hospitality, chastity, truth, respect for elders, hard work and good character will automatically take its course in due time. With its mammoth population, and massive potential, Africa will get rid of moral - back sliding and come to its senses despite all the challenges.

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